

Excess thermodynamic properties of ternary liquid mixtures of xylenes with butyl acrylate and methyl methacrylate solvents at 303, 308 and 313 K

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Abstract : Ultrasonic velocity (U), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) for the ternary liquid mixtures of butyl acrylate + methyl methacrylate + *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene have been measured as a function of the composition at 303, 308 and 313 K. The experimental data have been used to calculate some excess thermodynamical parameters, such as viscosity (η^E), adiabatic compressibility (β^E), free volume (V_f^E), Gibb's free energy (ΔG^E) and Grunberg's interaction parameter (d). These excess magnitudes are discussed qualitatively in terms of the nature and type of intermolecular interactions of the components involved.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, compressibility, free volume, Gibb's free energy, interaction parameter.

Introduction

Ultrasonic velocities, densities, viscosities and derived thermodynamic and acoustical parameters are of considerable interest in understanding the inter molecular interactions in binary¹⁻³ and ternary⁴⁻⁷ liquid mixtures. The thermodynamic properties of multi-component liquid mixtures and their analysis are important in an industrial process. The mixing of different compounds gives rise to solutions that generally do not behave ideally. The deviation from ideality is expressed by many thermodynamic variables, particularly by excess or residual extensive properties. Excess thermodynamic properties of mixtures correspond to the difference between the actual value of an extensive property and the value it would have if the system behaved ideally, and thus are useful in the study of molecular interactions and arrangements. In particular, excess properties reflect the interactions that take place between (solute + solute), (solute + solvent) and (solvent + solvent) species. The present work provides data for the characterization of the molecular interactions between solvents and commercially important monomers, in particular, the influence of the chemical structure of the solute in the systems under consideration. Xylene is an aromatic hydrocarbon and it is largely used in the production of phthalic acid. Aromatic hydrocarbons are

very important to the petrochemical industry. Among these are benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene, which are basic raw materials for the production of a number of important petrochemicals. The monomers considered in this study are important industrial chemicals used in the large-scale preparation of useful polymers and are also interesting because they contain both a double-bond and an ester group.

Keeping these important aspects in view, the measurements on ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity for the ternary liquid mixtures of xylene with solvent binary mixtures of butyl acrylate and methyl methacrylate at 303, 308 and 313 K have been undertaken. The experimental data have been used to calculate some excess thermodynamical parameters, such as viscosity, adiabatic compressibility, free length, free volume, internal pressure, Gibb's free energy and Grunberg's interaction parameter. The variation of excess parameters on composition has been used to explain the nature and extent of intermolecular interactions in these mixtures. Moreover, literature survey indicates that no physico-chemical study on these systems has been reported. Therefore, the study of inter molecular interactions in these systems will be interesting owing to their applications.

Theory :

Various physical and thermodynamical parameters are calculated from the measured data such as

$$\text{Adiabatic compressibility } \beta = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

where U is ultrasonic velocity and ρ , the density.

$$\text{Free volume } V_f = \left(\frac{M_{\text{eff}} U}{k \eta} \right)^{3/2} \quad (2)$$

where M_{eff} is the effective molecular weight ($M_{\text{eff}} = \sum m_i x_i$, in which m_i and x_i are the molecular weight and the molefraction of the individual constituents respectively). k is a temperature independent constant which is equal to 4.28×10^9 for all liquids and η is the viscosity of the liquids.

The Gibb's free energy can be estimated from the following relation.

$$\Delta G = K_B T \ln \left(\frac{K_B T \tau}{h} \right) \quad (3)$$

where K_B is the Boltzman's constant ($1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ JK}^{-1}$), T the absolute temperature, ' h ' the Planck's constant (6.626

$\times 10^{-34} \text{ Js}$) and τ is the relaxation time $\left(\tau = \frac{4}{3} \eta \beta \right)$.

Excess values of the above parameters can be determined using

$$A^E = A_{\text{exp}} - A_{\text{id}} \quad (4)$$

where $A_{\text{id}} = \sum A_i X_i$, A_i is any acoustical parameters and X_i the molefraction of the liquid component. Grunberg

and Nissan⁸ formulated the following relation between the viscosity of a binary liquid mixture and pure components.

$$\ln \eta_{\text{mix}} = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_1 X_2 d \quad (5)$$

On applying to a ternary liquid mixture, this equation takes up the form

$$\ln \eta_{\text{mix}} = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + X_3 \ln \eta_3 + X_1 X_2 X_3 d \quad (6)$$

where d is an interaction parameter regarded as a measure of the strength of molecular interactions between the mixing components.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of pure liquids and for the ternary liquid systems at 303, 308 and 313 K have been given in Tables 1 and 2. The values of excess viscosity (η^E), excess adiabatic compressibility (β^E), excess free volume (V_f^E), excess Gibb's free energy (ΔG^E) and the Grunberg's interaction parameter (d) have been shown in Tables 3 and 4.

The thermodynamic excess properties are found to be more sensitive towards intermolecular interaction between the component molecules of liquid mixtures. The sign and extent of deviation of excess properties depend on the strength of interaction between unlike molecules⁹. According to Fort *et al.*¹⁰, the variation of excess viscosity gives the strength of the molecular interaction between the interacting molecules. For systems where dispersion, induction and dipolar forces which are operated by the values of excess viscosity are found to be nega-

Table 1. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of pure liquids at 303, 308 and 313 K

Organic liquids		ρ (kg m ⁻³)			η ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			U (m.s ⁻¹)		
		303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
Butyl acrylate	Expt. value	888.8	882.8	876.2	0.7458	0.6782	0.6366	1175.8	1160.6	1143.3
	Lit. value	893.9 ¹⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Methyl methacrylate	Expt. value	929.4	916.4	903.0	0.6134	0.5594	0.5229	1165.50	1144.4	1123.2
	Lit. value	937.6 ¹⁸	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>o</i> -Xylene	Expt. value	870.6	867.8	862.96	0.7432	0.6705	0.6623	1329.2	1320.7	1303.9
	Lit. value	871.5 ¹⁹	867.0 ²¹	-	-	0.6690 ²⁰	-	1330.0 ¹⁹	1321.0 ²⁰	-
<i>m</i> -Xylene	Expt. value	854.5	850.8	846.2	0.6159	0.5340	0.4938	1320.8	1279.8	1263.5
	Lit. value	855.5 ¹⁹	851.6 ²¹	-	-	0.5229 ²⁰	-	1322.0 ¹⁹	1281.0 ²⁰	-
<i>p</i> -Xylene	Expt. value	852.9	848.2	845.4	0.6499	0.5514	0.5071	1290.8	1270.2	1258.5
	Lit. value	852.5 ¹⁹	848.2 ²¹	-	-	0.5501 ²⁰	-	1292.0 ¹⁹	1268.0 ²²	-

Table 2. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) at 303, 308 and 313 K for

Molefraction (X_3)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)			η ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			U (m.s ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System-I : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>o</i> -xylene (X_3) [(X_1)/(X_2)=3 : 1]									
0	896.1	892.2	887.7	0.7396	0.6639	0.5864	1175.8	1154.9	1133.5
0.02	895.9	891.6	888.6	0.7259	0.6605	0.5805	1178.8	1158.5	1136.4
0.04	895.6	891.1	887.1	0.7129	0.6556	0.5671	1180.3	1159.0	1138.6
0.06	894.5	890.8	885.6	0.7023	0.6331	0.5437	1181.6	1160.8	1140.4
0.08	892.2	890.1	885.1	0.6921	0.6321	0.5202	1182.9	1161.8	1141.2
0.10	891.0	889.6	884.3	0.6894	0.6254	0.5183	1184.7	1163.7	1142.7
System-II : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>m</i> -xylene (X_3)									
0	896.1	892.2	887.7	0.7396	0.6639	0.5864	1175.8	1154.9	1133.5
0.02	892.8	887.8	886.2	0.7300	0.6670	0.5807	1176.8	1155.4	1135.8
0.04	891.1	887.1	884.4	0.7270	0.6603	0.5700	1178.0	1156.8	1136.6
0.06	889.1	886.7	883.2	0.7140	0.6366	0.5675	1179.8	1157.2	1138.2
0.08	888.9	885.9	881.9	0.6976	0.6329	0.5309	1180.9	1159.9	1140.8
0.10	887.6	885.2	880.8	0.6896	0.6284	0.5263	1182.4	1160.5	1141.9
System-III : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>p</i> -xylene (X_3)									
0	896.1	892.2	887.7	0.7396	0.6639	0.5864	1175.8	1154.9	1133.5
0.02	894.9	891.6	885.3	0.7319	0.6718	0.5857	1176.2	1155.0	1134.3
0.04	893.2	890.9	884.9	0.7295	0.6648	0.5822	1176.9	1155.6	1136.2
0.06	892.4	889.9	883.6	0.7153	0.6382	0.5795	1177.6	1156.8	1136.9
0.08	891.8	887.4	882.3	0.6963	0.6343	0.5425	1178.9	1158.8	1137.1
0.10	890.5	886.9	881.0	0.6901	0.6305	0.5389	1180.1	1159.4	1137.8

Table 3. Excess values of viscosity (η^E) and adiabatic compressibility (β^E) at 303, 308 and 313 K for

Molefraction (X_3)	η^E ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			β^E ($\times 10^{-10}$ m ² N ⁻¹)		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System-I : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>o</i> -xylene (X_3) [(X_1)/(X_2) = 3 : 1]						
0	0.0269	0.0154	0.0217	0.0119	0.0134	0.0252
0.02	-0.0126	-0.0116	-0.0289	0.0201	0.0025	0.0101
0.04	-0.0010	-0.0063	-0.0432	0.0068	0.0357	0.0298
0.06	-0.0122	-0.0167	-0.0677	0.0165	0.0483	0.0555
0.08	-0.0230	-0.0181	-0.0923	0.0504	0.0761	0.0868
0.10	-0.0263	-0.0253	-0.0952	0.0652	0.0893	0.1540
System-II : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>m</i> -xylene (X_3)						
0	0.0269	0.0154	0.0217	0.0119	0.0134	0.0252
0.02	-0.0193	-0.0208	-0.0251	0.0275	0.0720	0.0035
0.04	-0.0182	-0.0164	-0.0336	0.0498	0.0825	0.0635
0.06	-0.0071	-0.0050	-0.0338	0.0666	0.1048	0.0756
0.08	-0.0073	-0.0064	-0.0681	0.0768	0.0975	0.0774
0.10	-0.0134	-0.0086	-0.0704	0.0915	0.1197	0.0983
System-III : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>p</i> -xylene (X_3)						
0	0.0269	0.0154	0.0217	0.0119	0.0134	0.0252
0.02	-0.0204	-0.0253	-0.0204	0.0153	0.0392	0.0620
0.04	-0.0193	-0.0202	-0.0219	0.0410	0.0587	0.0623
0.06	-0.0064	-0.0044	-0.0226	0.0597	0.0720	0.0918
0.08	-0.0113	-0.0064	-0.0576	0.0680	0.0886	0.1249
0.10	-0.0163	-0.0082	-0.0591	0.0845	0.1064	0.1525

Table 4. Excess values of free volume (V_f^E), Gibb's free energy (ΔG^E) and interaction parameter (d) at 303, 308 and 313 K for

Molefraction (X_3)	$V_f^E (\times 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1})$			$\Delta G^E (\times 10^{-21} \text{ KJ mol}^{-1})$			d		
	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
System-I : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>o</i> -xylene (X_3) [$(X_1)/(X_2) = 3 : 1$]									
0	-0.1547	-0.1235	-0.1985	0.1444	0.1070	0.1210	0.22	0.14	0.18
0.02	0.0631	0.0902	0.2693	-0.0703	-0.0825	-0.1050	-5.79	-5.83	-12.46
0.04	0.0206	0.0589	0.4209	-0.0072	-0.0684	-0.2570	-0.23	-1.85	-10.12
0.06	0.0912	0.1284	0.7017	-0.0395	-0.0589	-0.4124	-1.52	-2.43	-12.11
0.08	0.1608	0.1326	1.0075	-0.0802	-0.0531	-0.5733	-2.35	-1.99	-12.60
0.10	0.1805	0.1899	1.0342	-0.0898	-0.0884	-0.5816	-2.28	-2.41	-10.88
System-II : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>m</i> -xylene (X_3)									
0	-0.1547	-0.1235	-0.1985	0.1444	0.1070	0.1210	0.22	0.14	0.18
0.02	0.1141	0.1775	0.2314	-0.1262	-0.1770	-0.1391	-8.41	-9.81	-10.74
0.04	0.1145	0.1525	0.3122	-0.1331	-0.1488	-0.1795	-4.20	-4.20	-7.69
0.06	0.0592	0.0115	0.3091	-0.0851	-0.0347	-0.1744	-1.47	-0.39	-5.68
0.08	0.0458	0.0225	0.7275	-0.0146	-0.0257	-0.4133	-0.52	-0.45	-9.14
0.10	0.0834	0.0305	0.7548	-0.0100	0.0242	-0.4207	-1.00	-0.60	-7.94
System-III : Butyl acrylate (X_1) + methyl methacrylate (X_2) + <i>p</i> -xylene (X_3)									
0	-0.1547	-0.1235	-0.1985	0.1444	0.1070	0.1210	0.22	0.14	0.18
0.02	0.1224	0.2113	0.1725	-0.1264	-0.1768	-0.0948	-8.83	-11.62	-8.49
0.04	0.1211	0.1831	0.1873	-0.1334	-0.1587	-0.0103	-4.38	-5.00	-4.78
0.06	0.0428	0.0111	0.1847	-0.0761	-0.0228	-0.0931	-1.32	-0.33	-3.63
0.08	0.0725	0.0253	0.5750	-0.0130	-0.0191	-0.3178	-1.00	-0.48	-7.60
0.10	0.1038	0.0335	0.5884	-0.0314	-0.0177	-0.3165	-1.31	-0.59	-6.56

tive, whereas the existence of specific interactions leading to the formation of complexes in liquid mixtures tends to make excess viscosity positive. The excess viscosity (Table 3) is positive with the absence of xylenes (X_3), but it founds negative with increasing the concentration of xylenes in all the three systems. From the analysis and close observation it is found that the excess values are decrease with increase in molefraction of X_3 and also with the rising of temperature. This behaviour shows that the existence of molecular interaction between the components of mixture for all the systems studied.

Table 3 shows the variation of excess adiabatic compressibility. The β^E values are positive over the whole composition range for all the mixtures and temperature too. However, these values are increases with increasing the molefraction of xylene also with elevation of temperature. Fort *et al.*¹⁰ found that the negative value of excess adiabatic compressibility indicated greater interaction between the components of the mixtures. Positive values in excess properties correspond mainly to the existence of dispersive forces. Further, the negative value

of β^E is associated with a structure making tendency while a positive value is taken to indicate the structure breaking tendency due to hetero-molecular interaction between the component molecules of the mixture. In the present investigation the positive β^E values for ternary mixtures may be attributed to the rupture of hydrogen bond between xylenes and acrylate solvent mixtures. Further, it is noticed that the strength of interaction get weakened with elevation of temperature in all systems studied¹¹.

Table 4 gives a qualitative picture of the excess free volume for the three ternary liquid systems. This indicates the extent of deviation from ideal with the molefraction of the mixtures. The excess values for all the three systems are found to be positive except the molefraction of X_3 at 0. Further, these values increases with increasing the molefraction of xylenes as well as with rising of temperature. These variations can be explained in terms of molecular interaction, structural effect and interstitial accommodation along with changes in free volume. The sign of V_f^E depends upon the relative strength between the contractive forces and expansive

forces. The factors responsible for volume contraction are :

- (a) Specific interaction between component molecules.
- (b) Interstitial accommodation of molecules of one component in to the vacant spaces of molecules of the other components. This occurs preferentially when the size difference between the component molecules is large, or when large gaps are available in the structural network of molecules.
- (c) Weak physical forces, such as dipole-dipole or dipole-induced dipole interactions or Van der Waal's forces.

The factors that cause expansion in volume are the following :

- (a) dispersion force,
- (b) steric hindrance of component molecules,
- (c) unfavorable geometric fitting,
- (d) electrostatic repulsion, etc.

The negative part of V_f^E curves of the system asserts that the combined effect of the factors responsible for volume contraction outweigh the combined effect of the factors causing volume expansion and vice-versa¹². Adgaonkar *et al.*¹³ showed positive value of V_f^E , indicating the existence of weak molecular interaction in the liquid mixtures. Fort *et al.*¹⁰ noticed that negative excess free volume tends to decrease as the strength of the interaction between the unlike molecules increases although they do not parallel with the excess compressibilities. However, in the present investigation the observed behaviour of V_f^E shows the strength of molecular interaction is weakened with the addition of xylene concentration as well as with rising of temperature. The magnitude of V_f^E values follows the sequence : *o*-xylene > *m*-xylene > *p*-xylene.

The variation of excess Gibb's free energy (Table 4) is found to be negative except for zero molefraction of X_3 in all systems studied. The values of ΔG^E decreases with increasing the molefraction of X_3 and also with rising of temperature. According to Reed *et al.*¹⁴, the positive ΔG^E may be attributed to specific interactions like hydrogen bonding and charge transfer while negative values may be ascribed to the dominance of dispersion forces¹⁵. In the present investigation, it is found that the negative value of ΔG^E shows the strength of interaction gets weakened with increasing of xylene content as well as with the elevation of temperature. Further the negative values of ΔG^E indicate the easier flow of ternary mixtures com-

pared with the behaviour of pure components¹⁶. The magnitude of the ΔG^E values are in the order : *p*-xylene > *m*-xylene > *o*-xylene.

The interaction parameters ' d ' in Grunberg *et al.*⁸ equation is a measure of the strength of interaction, between the mixing components. d -values were said to indicate various types of interaction¹⁷. Large and positive d -value indicated strong specific interaction; small positive value indicated weak specific interaction and large negative value indicated no specific interaction. It is evident from Table 4 that d -value is negative in all the three systems studied except zero molefraction of X_3 . It is seen that the values of d increase with increasing the molefraction of X_3 for every mixture and the same decreases with rising of temperature. The negative values of ' d ' may be attributed to the dominance of dispersive interaction arising from the breaking of hydrogen bonding of xylene makes the mixture to flow more easily. Further, the increasing behaviour of d -values exhibits the existence of molecular interaction between the unlike molecules. But, however, the strength of interaction gets weakened with the increase of temperature which may be due to decreasing behaviour of d -values for all systems studied. The magnitude of ' d ' values in the order : *p*-xylene > *m*-xylene > *o*-xylene.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in this present research works are analytical reagent (AR) and spectroscopic reagent (SR) grades of minimum assay of 99.9% obtained from E. Merck, Germany and SdFine chemicals, India, which are used as such without further purification. The purities of the above chemicals were checked by density determination at 303, 308 and 313 K which showed an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-7}$ kg m⁻³ with the reported values¹⁸⁻²¹. The ternary liquid mixtures of different known compositions were prepared in stopper measuring flasks. The density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity were measured as a function of composition of the ternary liquid mixture of xylenes which added to the binary mixture of butyl acrylate and methyl methacrylate at 303, 308 and 313 K. For this purpose, binaries with fixed ratios $X_1/X_2 \cong 3 : 1$ were prepared by volume. The density was determined using a specific gravity bottle by relative measurement method. The weight of the sample was measured using electronic digital balance with an accuracy of ± 0.1 mg (Model : Shimadzu AX-200). An Ostwald's viscometer (10 ml) was used for the viscosity measurement. Efflux time was determined using a digital chronometer to within ± 0.01 s. An ultrasonic interferometer having the frequency of 3

MHz (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, Model : F-81) with an overall accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ has been used for velocity measurement. An electronically digital operated constant temperature bath (RAAGA Industries) has been used to circulate water through the double walled measuring cell made up of steel containing the experimental solution at the desired temperature. The accuracy in the temperature measurement is ± 0.1 K.

Conclusion :

Ultrasonic method is a powerful tool for characterising the physico-chemical properties and existence of molecular interactions in the mixture. Excess ultrasonic properties of ternary mixtures of xylenes in butyl acrylate and methyl methacrylate at 303, 308 and 313 K are considered to be a reflecting agent of magnitude of polarity and size of interaction in the molecules. The strength of interaction tends to be weaker with addition of xylenes content as well as with rising of temperature due to the presence of weak intermolecular forces and thermal dispersion forces. From the magnitude of ΔG^E and 'd', it can be concluded that the strength of molecular interaction is in the order : *p*-xylene > *m*-xylene > *o*-xylene.

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